
Mysticism: A Way for Christian-Muslim Dialogue

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Abstract: Sufism and Mystical experience of the Christian East can be a common ground for dialogue. The Semitic religions have many common elements to look into for the dialogue. The Mystical experience of the Sufism (Islam) and mysticism in Christian East one of the elements, where we can come together in dialogue. Both these religions have a spiritual experience in mysticism, where they understand the 'oneness' of God and expression of this 'oneness' is seen in the life of the believer as following the commandments. This experience is not merely an academic, instead it is an intimate and transforming encounter with God, where both experience compassionate and merciful creator. This enables theme to do the service because, they have come across the God as loving creator to whole humanity. .

Keywords: Dialogue, Mysticism, Oneness with God, Sufism, Muslim-Christian Dialogue

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Introduction

Sufism and Mystical experience of the Christian East can be a common ground for Christian, Muslim Dialogue, because there are common elements in both traditions. The mystical experiences of each tradition enable Christians and Muslims to understand each other as children of God. The mystical experience of the early Christian communities and the Sufi mystical experience of brotherhood is one of the paths, which can promote a deep and lasting collaboration between Christians and Muslims. This is because the mystical experiences of the persons of both traditions have several common traits. According to McIntosh we often use the term ‘mysticism’, though this is really something of an academic invention; earlier eras referred to the most intimate and transforming encounter with God as ‘contemplation’ (McIntosh, 1998: 11). If we analyse the goal of every mystic, we realize that it is God. In this essay, I would like to explore some of the possibilities of Christian, Muslim dialogue on the basis of the mystical experience of both religions, which enables ‘interfaith dialogue in the present world’.

1. Early Islam in the Eastern Christian World

“The Middle East and North Africa are the cradle(s) of not only Christianity but also of two other great religions, Judaism and Islam. Despite a mutual origin, pressure is building up on the Christians in this region” (Riemenschneider, 2011: 6). Since its inception Islam has had a great contact with Christianity. ‘Muslim-Christian communication is as old as Islam (Saab, 1964: 43). During the time of the Islamic birth in the Arabian Peninsula and spreading in the eastern provinces of Byzantium, there were lot of conflicts between the Byzantines and the local Christian communities, which had created so many conflicts and wars (Thomas et al., 2006: 1), which, in fact an easy access to the new religion to spread. Indeed, all “The Arab conquests of the Byzantine eastern provinces and the consequent establishment of Muslim dominance foreshadowed the end of the long tradition of Hellenism in western Asia” (Grypeou et al., 2006: 1). But,

one can see both negative and positive the relationship between Christianity and Islam. Though the religions had also cordial in many places since its inception. John of Damascus is an example of the cordial relationship with the Caliph as his secretary followed by his father and grandfather (Thomas, 2005: 11), but he considers Islam as the sum of all heresies.

William Dalrymple, a Scottish historian, made two important observations on Christian Muslim relationship while traveling throughout the Middle East several years ago. First, he observed that while visiting ancient cells of monks near the Monastery of Mar Saba in the Israeli-Occupied West Bank, every cell had a prayer niche almost identical to the mihrab, which is a basic feature of all mosques today (Sharp, 2012: 11). He concluded that, “. . . the prayer niche must be another of those features of the early Christian world which has been lost to modern Western Christianity, yet which is still preserved in Islam” (Sharp, 2012: 11). “Dalrymple’s second observation attests to a truth that Orthodox Christians and Muslims have known instinctively for centuries— that they originally came from one civilization and share the same ancestry” (Sharp, 2012: 12). Though they had a deep relationship with each other. The Islamic tradition as it is developing gradually puts more and more emphasis on the “Arab” nature of Muhammad and Islam. It is true that in the beginning, there is an appeal to commonality—not of ancestry so much as of salvation-history. However, as time goes on, it becomes important for Muslim tradition to distance itself from any dependency on the pre-existing Christian and Jewish “civilizations,” and to trace its ancestry to Abraham back through the line of Ishmael and Hagar.

1.1 Early Islamic Growth in the Middle East

The presence of Christians in the Arab Peninsula had influenced Islam in its creation of Islamic theology. “The confrontation of Christianity with the early theological and political development of Islam addresses broader questions of intercultural relations and reciprocities and their impact on the

formation of religious systems and identities” (Thomas et al., 2006: 4). Early Islam had direct contact with Syriac Christians (Thomas et al., 2006: 4), which separated at the Council of Ephesus in 431 AD (Angold, 2006: 511), as part of the Nestorian heresies and emphases that radical distinctions between the two natures of Jesus Christ, Jacobite Christians (Angold, 2006: 511), which separated at the council of Chalcedon in 451 AD (Angold, 2006: 511), and there were also Arab Christians who had a direct communion with Byzantium church. “Arabic and Syriac Christianity contributed to the emergence and rapid spread of Islam, and especially the specific Christian elements in the cult and faith that were formative upon Islam and became part of its tradition” (Thomas et al., 2006: 4). So, the relationship between the churches in Roman empire as well as Persian empire had influenced theological development of Islamic formation.

The early Muslims also had contacts with Maronite Christians and Alexandrian Christians. Ibn Jubayr, an Arab geographer and poet says, “It is strange how the Christians round Mount Lebanon, when they see any Muslim hermits, bring them food and treat them kindly, saying that these men are dedicated to Great and Glorious God and that they should therefore share with them” (Saab, 1964: 44) Syria is another place where Islam encountered Christianity. The Christianity in Syria was the product Nestorian heresy (Some Christians in Syria would have held a Nestorian position, but Syrian Christianity was not produced by Nestorianism), who separated at the Council of Ephesus from the main church. They were called the Assyrian Church of East. ‘Coming to the development of religious systems within the ‘Syriac Society,’ Toynbee says that the Babylonian challenge produced two religious’ movements: Judaism with its later development, Christianity, and Zoroastrianism (Siddiqi, 1964:118). Ethiopia is another country Islam had connection from the beginning. “Ethiopia became a Christian state in about 300 A.D. Muslims and Christians have been living side by side in the region since the time when the Prophet Mohammad sent some of his followers there for sanctuary in 615 (Shetler &

Yehualashet, 2013: 319). The relationship between these two religions was both cordial as well as conflict type.

1.2 Early Islam with Christianity and Idol Worshipers

In the fourth century, many Arab tribes joined Christianity following the teaching of the Church of the East (Thomas, 2007: 2). The prophetic revelation was given in two places called Mecca and Medina for 23 years. In Mecca, Muhammad had to encounter with Arab paganism where he was emphasizing on morality, but in Medina the situation was different there, he comes across, Judaism and Christianity. “Communication between Christianity and Islam began with the revelation of the Qur’an. As it was revealed to Muhammad in the seventh century in a peninsula, which was partly Christian, communication between Christianity and Islam became an integral part of the Quran” (Saab, 1964: 43). Prophet Muhammad had a very close relationship with Christianity, which was friendliness most of the times, because Muhammad was comfortable with the idea of monotheism which opposite to idol worshippers of the tribes in the Arabian Peninsula. “The Quran describes the Christians as the closest community to Islam” (Saab, 1964: 43) in many times. There were also times Quran critics the Christian theology such as Trinity, which goes against monotheism, Muhammad believes.

1.3 Trinity: Unity of God

“Twice the Quran criticises those who confess the Trinity. Sura 5: 72–73 calls on Christians to give up adding gods to the One True God” (Beaumont, 2012: 111). ‘They have certainly disbelieved who say, “Allah is the Messiah, the son of Mary” while the Messiah has said, “O Children of Israel, worship Allah, my Lord and your Lord. Indeed, he who associates others with Allah - Allah has forbidden him Paradise, and his refuge is the Fire. And there are not for the wrongdoers any helpers.” (Q 5:72) The second passage in which the Trinity is challenged is sūra 4:171. People of the Book, do not exaggerate in your religion. Only speak the truth about God. Christ Jesus, son of Mary, was

the messenger of God, and His word which He cast on Mary, and a spirit from Him. Believe in God and His messengers and do not say “Trinity”; give it up for your own good. Surely God is One God (Beaumont, 2012: 111). These early attitudes of Islam made it very difficult for Christians to encounter Muslims because the revelation which they have received in the Incarnation (Word became Flesh) mystery is the truth to them.

Christians believed that Jesus is the Incarnated Logos (Jn 1;14) “For Christians direct or supernatural revelation came only to the Jewish people and found its fulfilment in Christ in his person and his gospel” (Knowles, 2011: 319). They also believed that the fullness of revelation in Jesus Christ; ‘in the past God spoke to our ancestors through the prophets at many times and in various ways, but in these last days he has spoken to us by his Son, whom he appointed heir of all things, and through whom also he made the universe. (Heb 1:1-2) They would need to defend their belief in God as one essence (*ousia*) in three persons (*hypostases*) which was shared by all denominations of the church in the Middle Eastern territories under Muslim rule. They may have been divided over their understanding of the union of the divine and human in Christ, but they were united in their faith in the Triune God. In a dialogue with the Caliph al-Mahdi- and Timothy I, Patriarch of the East Syrian (Nestorian) Church said, “That Christians believe in ‘three *hypostases* (*aqānīm*) . . . The Father, the Son and the Holy Spirit, which are together one God, one nature, and one essence (*jawhar*)” (Beaumont, 2005: 115). It is the fundamental mystery of Christianity. Timothy explained to the caliph, “Just as the Caliph is one person in his mind and spirit, and these cannot be separated from him, so it is with God and his Word and Spirit” (Beaumont, 2005: 115). He believed that Jesus taught this great mystery clearly in the gospel and we can experience this mystery by studying created things.

“Gregory the Theologian claimed that Abraham received a vision of God, not in his role as deity, but as a man. Augustine of Hippo affirmed Abraham’s understanding of the Unity of the Trinity: while greeting the three strangers, Abraham confessed to

one God in three hypostases” (Strezova, 2014: 176-177). John of Damascus defended Trinity in Damascus, perhaps already at the monastery of Mar Saba near Jerusalem. John reports that Muslims accuse Christians of associating Christ with God in an unacceptable way because Christians say that “Christ is the Son of God and God. John suggests that Christians should quote the Muslim belief that ‘Christ is the Word and Spirit of God’ and say ‘if the Word is in God it is obvious that he is God as well” (Beaumont, 2005: 113).

Abū Qurra (d.c.830), Abū Rā’ita (d.c.835) and Ammār al-Bas. rī (d.c.860) who all attempted to defend and explain the Trinity in Arabic for a Muslim audience that was increasingly involved in debate with Christian intellectuals (Beaumont, 2005: 116). Abū Qurra says, “Christians do not believe in three gods when they say that the Father is God, the Son is God, and the Holy Spirit is God; and that the Father, the Son and the Holy Spirit are one God even though each of them is complete in himself” (Beaumont, 2005: 117). He is very sure that those who negate the Christian teaching object to the Trinity because their reason is confused by the Christian claims that the Father, the Son and the Holy Spirit are three hypostases (*aqānīm*) in one God (*ilah wāhid*), and that each of the hypostases is perfect God in himself (Beaumont, 2005: 117). “But Abū Qurra recognizes that the analogy with three men must not lead to the supposition that the Father, Son and Holy Spirit are separated or differentiated, since they would then be three divine beings rather than one divine being (Beaumont, 2005: 117).” He has supplied *wajh/ wujūh* as a translation of the Greek term *prosōpon* (person) which was a synonym for hypostasis in Greek (Beaumont, 2005: 117). So, he refers to the divine nature in various ways. The three persons (*wujūh*) share the same nonphysical nature (*latafa*). Therefore, each of the persons shares the same essence (*dhāt*). The three persons share the same oneness of divinity (*wāh.idiyya al-lāhūt*) (Beaumont, 2005: 117).

“The first pillar of Islam is essentially a foundational pillar, which forms the backdrop of all the other pillars of Islam. This

pillar consists of two testimonies the utterance of which enters one into the fold of Islam. The first part of the testimony is *Ash-hadu alaa ilaaha ilallah* (to testify there is nothing worthy of worship except” (Mirza & Bakali, 2010: 53). The worship is only to Allah. There are no gods except God. “The central creed of Islam consists of the two testimonies of faith or *Shahddahs*, which state that: There is no god but God, Muhammad is the Messenger of God” (“Common Word between Us and You,” 2008: 243). This testimony is an utterance of pure monotheism negating the belief in all other deities, other than God (Mirza & Bakali, 2010: 53), which was popular among the Arabian tribes. The prophet had come across two types of people in the Arabian Peninsula. In Mecca he had encountered with Arabian Paganism. They were idol worshippers. In Medina, he had to encounter with Judaism and Christianity, which also influenced him to affirm for the monotheism. He was totally against idol worshippers. “God is absolute and therefore devotion to him must be totally sincere” (“Common Word between Us and You,” 2008: 245). The testimony of faith emphasizes: “There is no god but God. it reminds Muslims that their hearts, their individual souls and all the faculties and powers of their souls (or simply their entire hearts and souls) must be totally devoted and attached to God” (“Common Word between Us and You,” 2008: 248). It is the total submission to God. The word *Islam* means submission. The Trinitarian God of Christianity is the sources of unity in the church. This unity of God enables the Christian to engage in dialogue with Islam who profess the same God (Lumen Gentium 16, Nostra Aetate 3). Being a committed Muslim one must able to submit oneself fully God because it is “God who has created all human beings equal in rights, duties and dignity, and who has called them to live together as brothers and sisters, to fill the earth and make known the values of goodness, love and peace” (Francis & Al-Tayyib, 2019) The ultimate aim is to encounter the creator, who created the whole human beings

1.4 The Quran and Early Christianity

“The Quran is the most important book in the Islamic lands, comparable to the Bible in the Western tradition. Transmitted orally, the text was soon committed to writing, and manuscripts - usually in the codex format - became the most common written work in circulation” (Blair, 2008: xx) Muslims believe that God reveals the word through the Angel Gabriel to Prophet Muhamad, who was illiterate. “That Muhammad was no theologian emerges on every page of the Koran. He was a preacher and a leader, political and military as well as religious”(Knowles, 2011: 318) It is the Arabic version that is considered by Muslims to be the true Quran, the direct word of Allah. No translation is considered to be the Quran or Word of Allah as such, and none has the same status as the original Quran. “The Quran, on the other hand, often appears to consider the Christians as a schismatic Jewish sect. They are included most of the time in what it says People of the Scriptures (*Ahl al-Kitâb*), judged mainly in the light of the Jews. Sometimes, however, Christians are presented in opposition to the Jews”(Ellul, 2007: 361).

In Christianity, the belief is that The Word became flesh and made his dwelling among us (Jn 1:14) in Jesus Christ, through the virgin Mary (Lk 1:27). It is the word, who was with God and he was God himself. (Jn 1:1-14) It is the pure word of God which enables creation. After Islamic rule had been established in the Middle East, the Christians found that the Muslims claim that the Quran is the only pure, all other scriptures are corrupt. (Beaumont, 2005: 195). “The earliest recorded Christian reading of the Qur’an comes from the writing of John of Damascus (d.c.750) who spent his career as a secretary to the Caliph in Damascus” (Beaumont, 2005: 195). John had three issues with Quranic understanding in Christian perspectives. They are: ‘The Quran contains material unworthy of divine revelation (Beaumont, 2005: 195), ‘the Quran shows Muhammad to be less than Muslims claim he is, (Beaumont, 2005: 197), ‘the Quran sometimes supports Christian beliefs (Beaumont, 2005: 198).

1.5 Jesus in Quran

Jesus is considered as a word of Allah in Quran, 'The Messiah, Jesus, the son of Mary, was but a messenger of Allah and His word which He directed to Mary and a soul from Him.' (Quran 4;171) and Quran also approves the virgin birth of Jesus. She said, "How can I have a boy while no man has touched me and I have not been unchaste?" He said, "Thus [it will be]; your Lord says, 'It is easy for Me, and We will make him a sign to the people and a mercy from Us. And it is a matter [already] decreed.'" (Quran 19;20-21). Jesus was also considered as a servant, 'Jesus was not but a servant upon whom We bestowed favour, and We made him an example for the Children of Israel.' (43;59). But the Quran disagrees that Jesus is not created. 'She said, "My Lord, how will I have a child when no man has touched me?" [The angel] said, "Such is Allah; He creates what He wills. When He decrees a matter, He only says to it, 'Be,' and it is.'" (Quran 3;47) the claim of John of Damascus is that "the Arian monk had given Muhammad mixed information about Christianity and this is echoed in the message of Muhammad. Support for Christian teaching can be found in the statement" (Beaumont, 2005: 198). Though John had a very prominent post in as secretary to caliph "John goes on to mock the teachings in the Quran about Christ, particularly that he was not crucified but only 'his shadow', and that he denied before God that he was his son, and continues to criticise Muhammad's unrestrained sexual appetite and what he regards as perverse teachings in various parts of the Quran" (Thomas, 2005: 11). "John thought Islam a false religion, based originally upon an encounter between Muhammad and a heretical Christian monk, from whom he gained some knowledge of the Bible. Thus, Islam can be dismissed as a Christian heresy since it has no integrity in itself, and whatever truthfulness or good it contained derived from the proper source of true teaching in the Bible" (Thomas, 2005: 11). Early Islam had a very deep relationship with Christianity which we have seen in the relationship on religious matters and political matters.

2. Eastern Mysticism and Sufism

“An ascetic and mystical element that was implicitly present in Islam since its very inception became explicit during the first Islamic centuries (the seventh and eighth centuries C.E.)” (Knysh, 2010: 1). Unlike Christian mysticism, the Islamic mysticism has not begun because of any persecution. One can say it has received an inspiration from Christian mysticism, which was popular in the Eastern and Western churches in the seventh and eighth centuries C.E. “This period witnessed the appearance of the first Muslim devotees and “moral athletes,” who formed primitive ascetic communities in the central and eastern lands of Islam, primarily in Mesopotamia, Syria and Eastern Iran”(Knysh, 2010: 1). Many people started following the early mystics as part of being away from the secular sphere and luxuries of the world. “As an outward sign of this pietistic withdrawal, some of them adopted a distinct dress code, which often featured a rough woollen robe.” (Knysh, 2010: 7). These mystics were known as Sufi saints in Islam. The word Sufism is a Latinised word which comes from the Arabic word *suf* which means wool (Knysh, 2010: 5). “By the end of the eighth century C.E., in the central lands of Islam the nick-name *suffiyya* (“wool-people” or “wool-wearers”) became a self-designation of those given to ascetic life and mystical contemplation” (Knysh, 2010: 7). Sufism became a prevalent characteristic of the Muslim social order in the later Middle Ages (12 – 6th Centuries CE).

2.1 Communion as the Community

The mystics in the early Islamic traditions were called “moral athletes” (Knysh, 2010: 7) and they formed as “*tariqas*” or “brotherhood” (Knysh, 2010: 5). Muslim mystics often trace this term to the root *Safà* with the general meaning of “purity;” to the phrase *ahl al-suffa* (“the People of the Bench”), that is, the pious and indigent companions of the Prophet who lived in his mosque” (Knysh, 2010: 7); in other words, we may tend to interpret that these mystics lived in a mosque under a head. The Constitution of the Society of Jesus describes the brotherhood

as ‘union of hearts.’ The ‘union of hearts’ is an expression of sincere communication between persons, which we see in the Acts of the Apostles in the Council of Jerusalem. Peter, as the head of the Apostles, and Paul as the head of the Church of Antioch, discussed and came to a decision on the controversy regarding the law of circumcision. “Certain people came down from Judea to Antioch and were teaching the believers: “Unless you are circumcised, according to the custom taught by Moses, you cannot be saved.” This brought Paul and Barnabas into sharp dispute and debate with them. So, Paul and Barnabas were appointed, along with some other believers, to go up to Jerusalem to see the apostles and elders about this question.” (Acts 15:1-2) “The early Christians considered that the Christian spirituality could not be experienced outside the community, which involved a multiplicity and variety of spiritual charisms” (Zizioulas, 1989: 27) because the Spirit was regarded as “communion” (Zizioulas, 1989: 27). They were living together and expecting the second coming of Christ as one body of Christ. The community life was an essential element among the early Christians. This type of community life was not just a living together under the same roof but it was a life of ‘union of hearts. It was a life of communion among the members. This communion helped them to forget the self and thus enabled them to love one another.

2.2 Self-Renunciation

It was discovered that there were many people who lived in search of a pure life as ascetics in the Arab-Byzantine region (Knysh, 2010: 6). “The acts of penitence and self-renunciation, which their practitioners justified by references to certain Quranic verses and the Prophet’s utterances, may be seen as a reaction against Islam’s newly acquired wealth that often led many faithful to abandon the frugal and heroic ways of self-denial associated with the original Muslim community in Medina” (Knysh, 2010: 2). It was evident from the correspondences of the early Christian hermits in the church. When the church had acquired freedom in the Roman Empire, many of the clerics enjoyed political status

too. They had forgotten the real value of Christ's teaching on self-renunciation, from which "arose a movement that in a variety of ways expressed a rejection of the conventional worldly values (Jean, 1989: 89).

Sufis also realized that many of these Umayyad and their officials were not following the spirit of the Holy Quran, which said, "Whatever you are given in this life is nothing but a temporary provision of this life and its glitter; what God has is better and more lasting. Will you not then understand?" (Quran 28:60). "They argued that the truly God-fearing person should try to save himself by withdrawing from the overbearing world and its sinful and unjust ways. "In an attempt to achieve this goal, the mystic had to contend not only with the corruptive trappings of the world, but also with his own base self (*nafs*), which Sufis see as the seat of egoistic evil lusts and passions impeding their progress towards God." (Knysh, 2010: 10). These ways of life are so much similar to the life adopted by the Christian ways of life in the deserts. Many of these people had very good contacts with the Christians of the Eastern countries like Syria and Constantinople. "This robe set them apart from people wearing more expensive silk or cotton. Wittingly or not, the early Muslim *religiosi* thereby came to resemble Christian monks and ascetics, who also donned coarse woollen clothes as a symbol of penitence and contempt for worldly luxuries" (Knysh, 2010: 7).

"Sufi movement developed a strict code of behaviour which encouraged repentance, abstinence from worldly delights, frugal living and voluntary poverty" (Knysh, 2010: 9), as we see among the early Christian hermits. "During the first century of Abbasid rule, renunciation was a widespread form of piety in Muslim communities. Renunciants (*zahid*) and pietists (*abid, andnasik*) of this period were not organised into a single homogeneous movement but came in different colours and stripes" (Karamustafa, 2007: 1). Self-renunciation is an important act of getting into the mystical life. The incarnation mystery of the Christian spirituality is a basis for the renunciation because being God, Jesus emptied himself and not considered himself equal to

God (Phil 2:7). instead, he renounced everything and entered into the world of human race. The person who has renounced himself has to enter into this stage where he tries to understand this mystery. Every mystic has to go through this experience in his life.

2.3 Purification

A person who desires to renounce everything in the world has to be purified. In each religion, there is a process called purification in different ways. “Mystics in every religious tradition have tended to describe the different steps on the way that leads toward God by the image of the Path. The Christian tripartite division of the *via purgativa*, the *via contemplativa*, and the *via illuminativa* is, to some extent, the same as the Islamic definition of *shari’a*, *tariqa*, and *haqiqa*” (Schimmel, 2011: 98). Naturally these paths are narrow and difficult to go through. In other words, these difficulties experienced by the person can be called the process of purification. The early mystics in the church left the cities in order to purify themselves. They were also doing the works of charity in the form of discourses and giving advices to the common people. The personal purification is very important in the mystical life. “Most of early Muslim ascetics emphasized personal purity, moral uprightness, fear of God and strict compliance with the letter of the Divine Law, there were those who carried their search of God’s pleasure a bit further” (Knysh, 2010: 8). In Sufism, “the ascetics, on the other hand, were allowed to practice self-imposed strictures which they deemed as preparation for the imminent Final Reckoning” (Knysh, 2010: 9). This purification process will make one to experience the ultimate or the absolute.

2.4 Union with the Absolute

The union of hearts among the mystics enables them to be one with the Heart of the Absolute. Mysticism is an experience of a Devotee “Seeing One’s Own Face in the Face of God” (Nelstrop & Podmore, 2016: 1). It will enable the person to “ascend beyond

cataphatic knowledge of God towards divine union, the divine idea became its entitlement and reality” (Nelstrop & Podmore, 2016: 1): This is one of the concepts called ‘Deification’ in Eastern Christianity and ‘Becoming Another Christ’ in Western Christianity. This personal experience can make these devotees from the two traditions of Sufis and Christian faith can engage in interfaith commitment in life.” Whatever be the Sufi approach to renunciation and to the question of how far to detach themselves from mainstream social life, some prominent renunciants and the renunciant communities that formed around them began to direct their energies increasingly to the cultivation of the inner life. This inward turn manifested itself especially in new discourses on spiritual states, stages of spiritual development, closeness to God, and love; it also led to a clear emphasis on ‘knowledge of the interior’ (*ilmal-batin*) acquired through ardent examination and training of the human soul” (Karamustafa, 2007: 2). The human soul forgets himself or herself and become one with the absolute. In the early church we come across the mystics forgetting themselves out of love towards the other. St. Ignatius of Antioch’s martyrdom story reminds us that even in suffering the name of Jesus was inscribed in his heart. “There is nothing left to distract the lover from God—the spiritual eye sees nothing but Him when the eye of the body is closed. He is enough for the loving soul: “O my Lord, whatever share of this world Thou dost bestow on me, bestow it on Thine enemies, and whatever share of the next world Thou doest give me, give it to Thy friends — Thou art enough for me” (Schimmel, 2011: 40). As the mystic feels that he is close to the heart of the absolute because he gets the awareness that his/her image and likeness (Gen 1:26) are the same as the creator. “The true knowledge of God was to be obtained by obedience to the uttermost” (Knysh, 2010: 36). The lost image and likeness has to regain through obedience.

2.5 Service and Love

“*Al-mu'min mir'at al-mu'min*, the faithful is the mirror of the faithful” — that is a Prophetic tradition that the Sufis considered

an excellent maxim for social intercourse” (Schimmel, 2011: 228). Sufi saint is the one who experiences the union of heart with the absolute and live in the world. He has the moral responsibility of looking after the other as the greatest commandment Christ gave to the rich man, “Love the Lord your God with all your heart and with all your soul and with all your mind.” This is the first and greatest commandment. And the second is like it: ‘Love your neighbour as yourself. All the Law and the Prophets hang on these two commandments.’ (Mt 22:36-40). The practical application of this maxim can be clearly seen in the Sufi history and leads to the one of the movement’s most nice aspects, namely, to the fraternal love, which originally came to exist among the Sufis of one community.

The parable of Good Samaritan is an example of a Christian commitment to the other which is emphasized much in Sufism. “Even Antony the Hermit recognized his total ignorance of divine mysteries and of the scriptures, and whose supreme value was love towards his neighbour” (Jean, 1989: 93): Service to humanity has always been one of the first phases in the preliminary steps of the path, but throughout his life it remains the true Sufi obligation (Schimmel, 2011: 228). For, “whoever excuses himself from the service of his brethren, God will give him a humiliation from which he cannot be rescued.” (Schimmel, 2011: 229). In Sufism the service to the other is considered as divine encounter. They were commonly referred to as *nussàk* (devout [men]), *zuhhàd* (world renouncers or ascetics), *ubbàd* (worshippers)—terms that roughly correspond to the Latin concept of *virii religiosi* (Knysh, 2010: 6). These religious men are not called to be under a roof for pious practice alone; instead, they have to go out into the world in order to do their work. “More than just fulfilling their religious duties, they paid close attention to the underlying motives of their actions and sought to impregnate them with a deeper spiritual meaning. This goal was achieved through a meticulous contemplation on the Qur’anic revelation, a thorough imitation of the Prophet’s piety, introspection as well as voluntary poverty and self-mortification.” (Knysh, 2010: 6). Love of God and love

of neighbour are essential practices in Christianity. Christians cannot isolate themselves from service to others.

“The Sufis distinguish three organs of spiritual communication: the heart (*qalb*), which knows God; the spirit (*ruh*), which loves Him; and the inmost ground of the soul (*sirr*), which contemplates Him” (Nicholson, 2007: 49). Christian mystics also invite the people of God into contemplation where the communication of the devotee to God is enable through heart and mind. Experiencing God is an innermost happiness of a mystics which can be seen in the both traditions. “Mystics of every race and creed have described the progress of the spiritual life as a journey or a pilgrimage” (Nicholson, 2007: 21) One can see this progress of spiritual journey in both these great traditions.

3. Towards Interfaith Befriending

The Pontifical Council for Interreligious Dialogue (PCID) aims at “the promotion of interreligious dialogue in accordance with the spirit of the Second Vatican Council, in particular the declaration “*Nostra Aetate*”. The PCID wants to have a good relationship among Christians and Muslims. “It promotes mutual understanding, respect and collaboration between Catholics and the followers of others religious traditions” (“The Pontifical Council for Interreligious Dialogue,” n.d.). There are two things very important in our interfaith dialogue. They are heart to heart relationship and participating in mutual Experiences.

3.1 Heart to Heart Relationship

“Too often the past missionary activity of Catholicism has been neither metanoia to new consciousness, new life and orientation, nor a life of grace and being graced, but a forced and imposed proselytism which Jesus himself rejected participating in mutual experience” (Cenkner, 1997: 130). Vatican Council II opened a new horizon for dialogue. In other words, one can say it was a heart-to-heart relationship because the Council encourages the Catholics to enter into dialogue with an open heart.

One document of Vatican Council II, *Ad Gentes* 9, acknowledged truth and grace in other religions in both the people and the traditions themselves. Other documents, *Lumen Gentium* 17 and *Gaudium et Spes* 11, spoke of the spirit of God filling the universe, even in the rituals and cultures of other faiths. Yet another, *Nostra Aetate* 2, called Catholics explicitly to interreligious dialogue and cooperation. (Cenkner, 1997: 132).

Pope Francis in his address to inter religious meeting in Abu Dhabi emphasized that one cannot understand God, the creator, without understanding human beings. Every human life is sacred. Everyone is important in the eyes of God. (“Apostolic Journey to the United Arab Emirates: Interreligious Meeting at the Founder’s Memorial (Abu Dhabi, 4 February 2019) | Francis,” 2019). God cannot be partial to anyone in particular because he created everyone in his image and likeness. The one who received the image from God can easily identify the other as the image of God. There will be mutual understanding from the Heart. Once a mystic identified this reality of God and the other, which will enable him to go ahead with relationship with the other.

But in reality, there is a lot of violence perpetrated between Christians and Islam. There are attacks in Syria. The migration into the European continent is another difficulties the western Christianity faces. The PCID gives a certain solution on such violence. Its message to Muslims for the end of Ramadam (18 May 2018) says:

To prevent and overcome these negative consequences, it is important that we Christians and Muslims recall the religious and moral values that we share, while acknowledging our differences. By recognizing what we hold in common and by showing respect for our legitimate differences, we can more firmly establish a solid foundation for peaceful relations, moving from competition and confrontation to an effective cooperation for the common good. This particularly assist those most in need, and allows us to offer a credible witness

to the Almighty's love for the whole of humanity. ("Message to Muslims for the End of Ramadam," The Holy See 2018).

Muslims and Christians frequently can meet in formal and informal ways as neighbours and friends. They can participate in festivals. They can organize inter faith prayers, even though Muslims and Christians worship separately in the mosques and churches, they join together. They can collaborate in social works. Coexistence does not mean giving up distinctive identities. Every religion has a distinct identity which will enable to appreciate the other. The document Human Fraternity speaks on dialogue as Dialogue, understanding and the widespread promotion of a culture of tolerance, acceptance of others and of living together peacefully would contribute significantly to reducing many economic, social, political and environmental problems that weigh so heavily on a large part of humanity; Dialogue among believers means coming together in the vast space of spiritual, human and shared social values and, from here, transmitting the highest moral virtues that religions aim for. It also means avoiding unproductive discussions; The protection of places of worship – synagogues, churches and mosques – is a duty guaranteed by religions, human values, laws and international agreements. Every attempt to attack places of worship or threaten them by violent assaults, bombings or destruction, is a deviation from the teachings of religions as well as a clear violation of international law (Francis & Al-Tayyib, 2019).

This kind of dialogue is possible if one really has faith in God. The document affirms that, everyone was created by same God. "In the name of God who has created all human beings equal in rights, duties and dignity, and who has called them to live together as brothers and sisters, to fill the earth and make known the values of goodness, love and peace" (Francis & Al-Tayyib, 2019). Being the children of same God, we brother and sisters. We are called to be the keepers of the other. The document says, "In the name of innocent human life that God has forbidden to kill, affirming that whoever kills a person is like one who kills the

whole of humanity, and that whoever saves a person is like one who saves the whole of humanity” (Francis & Al-Tayyib, 2019).

3.2 Participating in Mutual Experiences

One has to enter into the space of the other in order to have religious experience of other. This religious experience will enable one to understand who he is. Entering into the space of other is a difficult task. The one who enters may not be accepted by the other. The incarnation spirituality gives a hope for the Christians to enter into the space of other. Jesus entered into the human space in order to be part of humanity in every sense. “A major challenge is creating spaces and means for “rubbing shoulders with diverse people in an increasingly pluralistic world. “Not only is there a call to “rub shoulders” with diverse peoples, but the call is to love our neighbours—our religious neighbours—in ways that push relational boundaries. Miroslav Volf argues that living with the “other” in peace is “an expression of our God given humanity” (King, 2016: 203). Human beings are created as social beings. There is a communication between all of them. The isolated human being cannot live a proper life. It is same with the isolated religion. No religion can live as an isolated entity. Every religion has a connection with other religion(s). The mutual sharing of religious experience of mysticism will enrich the other. This will enable to flourish and nurture the identity of the other and enable to go forward in a peaceful life and well-being. “Interfaith dialogue has emerged as a major means for interacting with peoples of different faiths that work toward achieving such goals.” (King, 2016: 204). *Nostra Aetate* is an invitation to Christians to enter into this dialogue of experiences.

The Church regards with esteem also the Moslems. They adore the one God, living and subsisting in Himself; merciful and all- powerful, the Creator of heaven and earth, who has spoken to men; they take pains to submit wholeheartedly to even His inscrutable decrees, just as Abraham, with whom the faith of Islam takes pleasure in linking itself, submitted to God. Though they do not acknowledge Jesus as God,

they revere Him as a prophet. They also honor Mary, His virgin Mother; at times they even call on her with devotion. In addition, they await the day of judgment when God will render their deserts to all those who have been raised up from the dead. Finally, they value the moral life and worship God especially through prayer, almsgiving and fasting (Nostra Aetate 3).

“Since in the course of centuries not a few quarrels and hostilities have arisen between Christians and Moslems, this sacred synod urges all to forget the past and to work sincerely for mutual understanding and to preserve as well as to promote together for the benefit of all mankind social justice and moral welfare, as well as peace and freedom” (King, 2016: 204).

The courage of otherness is the heart of dialogue, which is based on sincerity of intentions. Dialogue is indeed compromised by pretence, which increases distance and suspicion: we cannot proclaim fraternity and then act in the opposite way. “The man who lies to himself and listens to his own lie comes to such a pass that he cannot distinguish the truth within him, or around him, and so loses all respect for himself and for others” (King, 2016: 204). The mutual sharing of experience can come from inter religious prayer. Faith in God is an essential element in the interfaith dialogue. Faith leads a believer to see in the other a brother or sister to be supported and loved. The document signed by His Holiness Pope Francis and the Grand Imam of Al-Azhar Ahmad Al-Tayyeb on ‘Human Fraternity’ goes like this, “Through faith in God, who has created the universe, creatures and all human beings (equal on account of his mercy), believers are called to express this human fraternity by safeguarding creation and the entire universe and supporting all persons, especially the poorest and those most in need” (Francis & Al-Tayyib, 2019). *Lumen Gentium* 16 says: “But the plan of salvation also includes those who acknowledge the Creator, in the first place amongst are Muslims; these profess to hold the faith of Abraham and together with us they adore the one merciful God who will judge humanity on the last day” (Lumen Gentium 16). Reconciliation,

a form of cooperation, requires some collective action Presuming an essential harmony of underlying interests between both faith communities, proponents of interreligious collective action for reconciliation seek to awaken similarly minded activists from different religious background (Francis & Al-Tayyib, 2019).

The common word between Christians and Muslims states,

The future of the world depends on peace between Muslims and Christians. The basis for this peace and understanding already exists. It is part of the very foundational principles of both faiths: love of the One God, and love of the neighbor. These principles are found over and over again in the sacred texts of Islam and Christianity. The Unity of God, the necessity of love for Him, and the necessity of love of the neighbor is thus the common ground between Islam and Christianity (Malik, 2013: 204).

The love commandment is given important in the statement. This is only possible through mutual participation and sharing. “ACW calls for future relations between Muslims and Christians to be predicated on acknowledging the primacy of the two commandments of love. These ethically salient affirmations suggest increased commitment to human equality and dignity and collaboration for the common” (“Common Word between Us and You,” 2008: 458).

Conclusion

The eastern Christians in the early Muslims’ kingdoms experienced freedom in many occasions. We have good examples as John of Damascus as the secretary to the caliph and Patriarch Timothy I had a very personal theological debate with the Caliph Al-Mahdi. There were also Arabic Christian theologians like Abū Qurra, Abū Rā’ita and Ammār al-Basrī who defend the unity of God in Arabic terms in order to create peaceful relationship in the Middle East countries. Dialogue is the place where we can find a common ground in order to work together. The focus must be given to more in common grounds of similarities rather than

disputes. Jesus is considered as a word of God and a prophet. The oneness of God will enable one to understand the Islamic and Christian mysticism as a common ground for dialogue.

There is a lot of misunderstanding and conflict among peoples of differing faiths in the twenty-first century, very particularly among Muslims and Christians. These misunderstandings and conflicts challenged not only religious sphere but also academic level, which moved peacebuilding and interfaith dialogue to the top of academic agendas. The basic need of the human being is love; in other words, every human being wants to live in harmony and peace. Most of the time, the means one takes to acquire peace and harmony is violence and conflicts. People believe that, if one destroys one's enemy, one can live in harmony. But it is impossible. The quest for living at peace with one another made theologians and missiologists to explore a theological ground, with a view to creating understanding and encouraging human encounters that foster respect and dignity for all peoples. "Peacebuilding is considered a relational approach to increase dialogue, mutual understanding, and trust between two conflicting groups. In praxis, peacebuilding reframes contexts of violence as opportunities to improve upon broken relationships and increase awareness of areas of commonalities and mutual interests" (Malik, 2013: 204). The mysticism invites the common people to engage in interfaith dialogue of life and experiences. Mysticism in both traditions emphasize on the oneness of God, who is compassionate and merciful. Mystics make their hearts awoken and experience the oneness of God within their hearts. The contemplation enables one to enter into this level of mystical experience. Love is the fundamental law among the mystics; love of one self, love of God and love of neighbour. The one who has experienced love cannot hate anyone, that is the challenge of mysticism; and it leads to service.

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